

THE RELATIONSHIP OF INDIVIDUAL CHARACTERISTICS AND NURSES CARING BEHAVIOR IN JOMBANG GENERAL HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Background: Public demands for the quality of health service increase highly and become the responsibility of hospitals. One factor affecting the quality of health services is nurses in providing nursing care (Mailani, 2017).

Objective: The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between individual characteristics with nurses caring behavior at Jombang General Hospital.

Methods: The research design used in this research is correlation analytic with cross sectional approach. The population used was all nurses in 4 internal rooms of the Jombang General Hospital with total sampling technique. The number of samples in the study were 58 nurses. The instruments used were questionnaires and analysis tests using Spearman-Rank.

Results: The results showed that the majority of respondents were 38 female respondents (65.5%), 35 respondents aged 3-45 years (55.2%), 40 respondents educated d3 nursing (70.7%), 47 respondents are married woman (81%), 21 respondents are working 1-5 years (36.2%). There are 45 respondents (77.6) have Nurse caring behavior. Based on Spearman-Rank test results, there is a relationship between age and nurses caring behavior with Sig. (2-tailed) 0.03 <0.05 and there is also a relationship between the length of work and the Sig. (2-tailed) 0.01 <0.05.

Conclusion: The good caring nurse behavior towards patients will improve the quality of hospital services and a good image for the hospital itself. This is because most of the number of employees in the hospital are nurses and automatically the most services are also provided by nurses.

Key words: Caring, nurse, individual characteristics.

INTRODUCTION

In improving nursing care, they should apply a caring attitude. Nurse caring behavior is very important for patients as service users that can help patient's healing process. In fact, there are still nurses who have not shown caring attitude to patients. This is indicated by the presence of nurses who do not have time to listen to clients (Rumagit, 2017). The nurses' assumption that therapeutic communication is less important is a factor that triggers the absence. There are a lot of factors cause nurses not to apply the principle of caring; one of which is the high workload that

makes nurses bored, which ultimately has an impact on work productivity and caring of nurses themselves (Desima, 2017).

Based on the results of several studies, it found many factors that influence nurses caring behavior towards patients. One factor is the emotional intelligence of the nurse. The results of the study at Bandung Regional Hospital showed that 74 respondents having high emotional intelligence tend to behave well and sufficient caring to patients (Darmini, 2017). Based on observations of interviews with patients to Jombang Regional Hospital, five respondents stated that there

were some nurses who were not prepared to be friendly to patients.

Caring is an action taken by nurses in providing health services to their patients. The caring behavior based on the ten factors will later affect patient satisfaction. Watson stated that what is meant by human care is an effort to protect, improve and maintain one's health status to remain in one's condition to improve one's knowledge and self-control. There are ten factors from Watson that can reflect nurses' behavior (Bagus, 2014). This study aimed to identify the individual characteristics of nurses and nurses' caring behavior at Jombang General Hospital, and also analyze relationship between individual characteristics of nurses and nurses' caring behavior at Jombang General Hospital.

METHODS

Study Design

The research used is correlation analytic with cross sectional approach.

Setting

This research was conducted in Jombang Regional Hospital.

Research Subject

The population used in the study were all nurses in 4 inpatients at Jombang Regional Hospital, totaling 58 respondents.

Instruments

The measuring instrument used in this study was caring behavior questionnaire that had previously been tested for validity and data from staffing. After the data is collected, then the data is processed and analyzed. The data processing consists of: editing, coding, scoring, tabulating and processing.

Data Analysis

After the data collection and processing is done, then the data obtained is analyzed by means of knowing the relationship to the variables, the SPSS test is performed using the Spearman-Rank.

Ethical Consideration

This research has gone through an ethical test from STIKES Husada Jombang and obtained permission from National Unity and Politics of Jombang Regency and director of Jombang Regional Hospital. The authors confirmed that all respondents had obtained appropriate informed consent.

RESULTS

Based on table 1, most female respondents behave well as many as 27 respondents (46.6%) and a small proportion behave less as many as 3 respondents (5.2%). Most male respondents behaved well as many as 18 respondents (31%). most respondents aged > 30-45 with good caring behavior as many as 28 respondents (48.3%) and none of them behaved less caring. Age <30 years mostly behaved good as many as 17 respondents (29.3%) and 3 respondents (5.2%) behaved less. Most of the respondents were educated D3 nursing with good caring behavior as many as 33 respondents (56.9%) and less caring behavior as many as 2 respondents (3.4%). Respondents who were educated S1 + nurses were 12 respondents (20.7%) with good behavior and 1 respondent behaved sufficiently (17.2%). Most respondents who are married have good caring behavior as many as 37 respondents (63.8%) and behave less as many as 2 respondents (3.4%). Unmarried respondents behaved well caring as many as 8 people (13.8%) and behaved less than 1 respondent (1.8%). Most respondents based on experience of work > 15 years of good caring behavior as many as 17 respondents (29.3%).

Respondents with less caring behavior with long working time < 1 year were 2 respondents (3.4%). Based on test results using the spearman rank, it is found that age is Sig. (2-tailed) 0.03 <0.05 which means there is a relationship between age and caring behavior. Characteristics of respondents based on length of work with

Sig. (2-tailed) 0.01 <0.05 which means there is a relationship between the length of work and caring behavior of nurses. Characteristics of respondents based on marital status, gender and educational background has no relationship ($p > 0.05$, $r = -0.63$; $p > 0.05$, $r = -0.224$; and $p > 0.05$, $r = -0.09$, respectively).

Examination of Relationship between Individual Characteristics and Nurses' Caring Behaviors in Jombang Regional Hospital Using Crosstabulation and Spearman Rank Test.

Table 1. Examination of Relationship between Individual Characteristics and Nurses' Caring Behaviors in Jombang Regional Hospital (n = 58).

Individual Characteristics	Nurses' Caring Behaviors						Total		p-value	r
	Less		Sufficient		Good		f	%		
	f	%	f	%	f	%				
Gender										
Male	0	0	2	3.4 %	18	31%	20	34.5%	0.08	-0.224
Female	3	5.2%	8	13.8%	27	46.6%	38	65.5%		
Total	3	5.2%	10	17.2%	58	77.6%	58	100%		
Age										
<30 years	3	5.2%	6	10.3%	17	29.3%	26	48.8%	0.03	0.413
>30-45 years	0	0	4	6.9%	28	48.3%	12	55.2%		
Total	3	5.2%	10	17.2%	45	77.6%	58	100%		
Educational Background										
D3 nursing	2	3.4%	6	10.3%	33	56.9%	41	70.7%	0.501	-0.09
S1 + nurses	1	1.7%	4	6.9%	12	20.7%	17	29.3%		
Total	3	5.2%	1	17.2%	45	77.6%	58	100%		
Marital Status										
Married	2	3.4%	8	13.8%	37	63.8%	47	81%	0.637	-0.63
Single	1	1.8%	2	3.4%	8	13.8%	11	19%		
Total	3	5.2%	10	17.2%	45	77.6%	58	100%		
Length of Work										
< 1 Years	2	3.4%	1	1.7%	0	0	3	5.2%	0.01	0.437
1-5 Years	1	1.7%	5	8.6%	15	25.9%	21	36.2%		
5-15 Years	0	0	4	6.4%	13	22.4%	17	29.3%		
> 15 Years	0	0	0	0	17	29.3%	17	29.3%		
Total	3	5.2%	10	17.2%	45	77.6%	58	100%		

$\alpha \leq 0.05$

DISCUSSION

Most respondents with female gender behave well as many as 27 respondents (46.6%) and a small proportion behave less as many as 3 respondents (5.2%). Some male respondents behaved well caring as many as 18 respondents (31%). According to Yang, he stated that there is no consistent

difference between men and women in problem solving skills, analytical skills, competitive encouragement, motivation, sociability or learning ability. There is no difference between women and men in nurses caring behavior. This is in line with the theory which said there is no difference between men and women.

Most respondents aged > 30-45 with good caring behavior were 28 respondents (48.3%) and none of them behaved less. Age <30 years mostly behaved caring well as many as 17 respondents (29.3%) and 3 respondents (5.2%) behaved less. Siagian (2010) asserts that the higher the age, the more it can show the maturity of the soul and the more able to think rationally, wisely, be able to control emotions and be open to the views of others. This opinion is supported by Desslerr (2000) which stated that the productive age is 25-45 years old. In this study, most respondents aged 30-45 behaved well caring. This is in accordance with the theory that the more mature someone's emotional intelligence the better that someone is. Another factor that in line with the theory is the experience of a nurse in dealing with a patient with a background.

Most of the respondents were educated D3 nursing with good caring behavior as many as 33 respondents (56.9%) and less caring behavior as much as 2 respondents (3.4%). Respondents who were educated S1 + nurses were 12 respondents (20.7%) with good behavior and 1 respondent behaved sufficiently (17.2%). Education is one way to assess the level of individual development; the goals to be achieved and the will developed. Individual education level is influenced by changes in attitudes, life behaviors and high curiosity. This is similar to the statement of Eskildsen et al. (2004) in Yang (2011) which states that highly educated employees will be relatively less satisfied with their work than those without tertiary education. Based on the results of the study, it was found that there was no difference in nurses caring behavior between those educated with D3 and S1 + nursing. Work experience is also an important factor in nurses caring behavior.

Most respondents who are married have good caring behavior as many as 37 respondents (63.8%) and less behavior as

much as 2 respondents (3.4%). Unmarried respondents behaved well caring as many as 8 people (13.8 percent) and behaved less than 1 respondent (1.8%). Marital status can be divided into two, namely married and unmarried. According to Hong et al. (1995) in Yang (2011), there are real differences in addressing a job, between individuals who are married and those who have not. Married individuals pay more attention to this work because of responsibilities towards the family so that it forces to increase responsibilities in marriage. Robbins (2006) who explains that marriage imposes increased responsibilities that make a permanent job more valuable and important. Someone who is married feels more secure with his current job, this is because they see it as a guarantee for his future.

Most respondents > 15 years with good caring behavior were 17 respondents (29.3%). Respondents with caring behavior less with long working time <1 year were 2 respondents (3.4%). Kreitner and Kinicki (2004) state that, long working periods will tend to make an employee feel more comfortable in an organization. This is because they have adapted to their environment long enough so that they will feel comfortable with his work. Other causes are also due to the policies of agencies or companies regarding life insurance in old age. Most respondents who have worked for more than < 1 year have a good caring behavior. This is in accordance with the theory that the longer a person works the better in adapting to the environment as well as in dealing with patients and patients' families with diverse cultural backgrounds. None of the nurses who worked > 15 years with less behavior.

Most respondents were female as many as 38 respondents (65.5%), they were divided into aged 3-45 years as many as 35 respondents (55.2%), educated D3 nursing

as many as 40 respondents (70.7%), the status of most were married as many as 47 respondents (81%), working years 1-5 years as many as 21 respondents (36.2%). Nurse caring behavior is mostly good as many as 45 respondents (77.6%). Based on the test results using Spearman Rank, there is a relationship between age and nurses caring behavior with Sig. (2-tailed) $0.03 < 0.05$ and there is a relationship between the length of work and the Sig. (2-tailed) $0.01 < 0.05$. According to Morrow, he stated that organizational commitment is influenced by personal character (individual) which includes age, years of service, education and gender, status (Prayitno, 2005). Humans have individual characteristics that differ from one another. A public service is not only influenced by the individual on performance. Managers/superiors also use subjective measures that are considerate to what is perceived by the evaluator/ community to improve the quality service of a hospital/ company (Hurriyati, 2005). Based on the results of the study, it was found that not all individual characteristics have a relationship with caring behavior of a nurse. Characteristics of individuals based on age and length of work that has a relationship with nurses caring behavior is in accordance with the theory that the more mature a person's age, the better the emotional intelligence as well as the length of work. Someone who has worked for more than 15 years becomes very comfortable in working because they already know the environment, the patients and families. Characteristics of respondents based on gender, status, education has nothing to do with caring behavior. This is influenced by several factors. In addition to formal education, nurses are also encouraged to update their knowledge through seminars, training and workshops. Gender has nothing to do with caring

behavior that men and women have. The marital status also has no relationship because unmarried employees will be given the same tasks and for new employees and an evaluation/ supervision will be carried out by superiors for their performance. This is because the employee concerned will continue or terminate the contract.

CONCLUSION

The results showed that the majority of respondents were female as many as 38 respondents (65.5%), aged 3-45 years as many as 35 respondents (55.2%), d3 educated nursing as many as 40 respondents (70.7%), having marital status were 47 respondents (81%), working years 1-5 years with 21 respondents (36.2%). Mostly nurse caring behavior is good as many as 45 respondents (77.6%). Based on the test results using Spearman-Rank, there is a relationship between age and nurses caring behavior with Sig. (2-tailed) $0.03 < 0.05$ and there is a relationship between the length of work and the Sig. (2-tailed) $0.01 < 0.05$.

SUGGESTION

Nurse caring behavior is very important for patients as service users in nursing services that help the patient in healing process.

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